

EVOLUTION OF ACADEMIC LIBRARY AND ITS SERVICES IN DIFFERENT ERA IN INDIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

Dr. Paramita Sen,

Librarian,

Chandraketugarh Sahidullah Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Berachampa, West Bengal, India.

ABSTRACT

The history of libraries is closely associated with human civilization. From the ancient days libraries existed in India and those are mainly academic libraries like Nalanda, Taxila, Vikramashila. The concept of libraries in modern world has changed from royal palace in ancient period to libraries without wall which can be accessed remotely from anywhere at any time. However, the libraries did not get the present state and shape in one day. With the changes of the civilization, the libraries has also changed its shape, collections and services. The medium of reading, the way of disseminating information, infrastructure -all changed with the advent of different era. The material on which the human thought is inscribed changes from clay tablet to tab. In ancient time, it was clay tablet, parchment, papyrus roll, palm leave. In medieval period, it was palm leave or parchment and in modern period with the invention of paper and printing, printed books replaced those previous ones. After that microform came, but now those entire medium are replaced very fast by the digital one. The ownership of library has also changed from royal palace and private library to public library. The services has also transformed from preservation to dissemination of information. The knowledge

became accessible, sharable and open to all. The present paper deals with a comparative study of the predominant characteristics of libraries especially academic libraries in India in different eras. This article describes the evolutionary changes the academic library gone through in different time periods, which can be broadly divided into ancient, medieval and modern. In ancient India, the biggest known university, the Nalanda University became a renowned seat of learning, its fame spreading beyond the boundaries of India. During the Medieval period, due to foreign invasions and political troubles, the higher education and the development of academic libraries were affected, though the powerful emperors patronized libraries in their own palaces. Monastery libraries also started to develop in the early middle ages. In modern India, during the British rule, number of academic libraries were established by the East India Company, and by the Christian missionaries. A huge change occurred in the structure, medium and collection of academic libraries in pre and post-independent India.

Key words: Library, academic library, history, evolution, library services, India

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1. Introduction

Our country has a glorious history, culture and heritage in every sphere of life from the ancient period. Many academic institutions established in ancient period. Our country played a role of torchbearer in the field of higher education. Students and scholars from outside India like Fa-hien, Hiuen Tsang came to learn and explore the treasure trove of knowledge kept in the academic libraries in the form of manuscripts in Indian Universities. Nalanda university library was one of the oldest and biggest academic libraries in the world. We were far advanced or ahead in every aspect of education than other civilizations of the then time. Donald G. Davis, Jr. of the University of Texas at Austin, writes on the status of library history in India that ‘although a core literature on Indian library history exists, it has many imbalances and gaps’. This article deals with the growth and development of academic libraries chronologically from ancient to modern period as recorded in different literatures on academic libraries.

2. Objective of the study

- i. Know the history and evolution of academic libraries in India
- ii. Depict the details of academic libraries from ancient to modern India
- iii. Compare the academic libraries with its different aspects in different era

3. Scope and limitations

Only the higher educational institutions like universities and colleges and their libraries are considered here for the study. The period covered from the inscription on stonewalls to present age of information technology.

4. Research methodology

This article is a comparison of the academic libraries in India from ancient to modern period. However, there is no hard and fast boundaries or outline from where we count the end of one era and start another one. Sometime, it may be overlapping. However, for the sake of research a time span is drawn here to show the evolution of academic libraries. The study is done by searching and reviewing the literature from different documentary sources related to the history of academic libraries in India.

5. Academic libraries in different era in India

5.1. Ancient period

In the Vedic age instructions were imparted orally, no writing materials were invented then. Taxila from 700 B.C. to 300 A.D. was considered the first institute of higher education in India. In 400 A.D., the Nalanda University, one of the biggest known universities spread its fame beyond the boundaries of India. Nalanda University Library was situated in a special area known by the name the Dharmaganja, comprised with three huge buildings, called the Ratnasagara, the Ratnodadhi and the Ratnaranjaka of which the Ratnasagara was a nine- storied building and housed the collection of manuscripts and rare sacred works on philosophy and religion. It contained texts relating to grammar, logic, literature, the Vedas, the Vedanta, the Dharmasastras, the Puranas, Astronomy, Astrology and Medicine. Bakhtiyar Khalji sacked it in 1197-1203 A.D. and set fire to the establishment of Nalanda.

The world famous universities, such as, the Vikramasila, the Vallabhi and the Kanchi were coming up in other parts of the country during the period from the 5th century A.D. to the

8th century A.D. Vallabhi University was famous for its Hinayana studies. This university had a good library is supported by royal grant for the purchase of books for the library.

The Jaggadal Vihara in Varendrabhumi was also an important centre of learning with collection of the reading material. The king Kampala, who ruled from 1084 to 1130 A.D., established it. The library of Mithila University played an important role in teaching and learning. It had a rich collection of various commentaries on the different branches of the Hindu Shastras. The university at Sompuri, also had its own library. Atisa Dipankar was a scholar of the university. This university was destroyed by fire in the middle of the 11th century A.D.

From 1083 to 1106 A.D., Navadwipa in Bengal reached its height of glory as a centre of intellectual excellence as well as its rich library facilities, when Lakshman Sen, a king of Gauda, made it his capital. The Nagarjuna Vidyapeeth, situated in South India at Amaravati, on the banks of river Krishna, flourished in about 7th century A.D. Its library housed in the top floor of the five-storied building of the university had an enormous collection on the Buddhist philosophy, scientific knowledge, such as botany, geography, mineralogy and medicine. There is enough archaeological evidence that supports the existence of this university and its library. It was a great attraction for scholars from the different parts of India and from countries, like, China, Burma and Ceylon. (*Majumder, 1946*)

5.2. Medieval period

5.2.1. Early middle

The existence of academic libraries during the medieval period of Indian history is not known in history, though the Muslim rulers had the libraries in their own palaces. There were many important royal and private libraries of the Sultana period. By the patronage of progressive rulers, many colleges and universities were established in different parts of the country. A library was attached to a college at Bidar, having a collection of 3000 books on different subjects. Aurangzeb got this Library transferred to Delhi to merge it with his palace library. During the medieval period, higher education and the development of academic libraries was affected due to Muslim invasions and political troubles.

5.2.2. Renaissance

After the depression of the dark ages, the late middle ages brought advancements in various aspects of life. From the 14th century renaissance movements spread which resulted in

the further establishment of non-religious libraries functioned as studying and meeting places of scholars who collected and produced written texts on various topics. With the rise of the renaissance, private collections became public; people get access to the precious collections stored in those private libraries. The emperors of the period had huge book collections in their royal palace. As it reached to the common people, the poets and writers of the period reached back to the antique texts and used them as their primary source of inspiration and collected, copied, translated the ancient writings, admiring the work of antique scholars. Invention of the printing press also made a drastic change.

During this period two important academic institution were established- Calcutta College in 1781 and Benaras Sanskrit College in 1792 by Jonathan Duncan. (*Kumar, 2014*)

5.3. Modern period

5.3.1. Industrial

5.3.1.1. Colonial

During the British rule in India, number of academic institutions were established by the East India Company and by the Christian missionaries. The Charles Wood dispatch of 1854 popularly known as the 'Magna Carta of English Education' in India also paved the way for the establishment of the universities in the presidency towns. Sir John Colville introduced the Bill to establish universities in India. As a result, three universities were established based on the London Universities Model in the Presidency towns -Calcutta, Madras and Bombay.

The Calcutta Fort William College was founded in 1800. All the colleges had their own libraries. During this period, particularly in the context of academic libraries, the important landmarks are - the Charter Act of 1813, the foundation of Fort William and Serampore Colleges, establishment of Calcutta, Madras and Bombay universities and their libraries, and Hunter Commission, Calcutta University Commission, library-training programmes. (*Srivastava, 1980*)

5.3.1.2. Post-colonial

The actual process for the development of the academic libraries in India have been set in motion with the appointment of the University Education Commission presided over by Dr. S. Radhakrishnan (1948-49) and the foundation of the UGC in 1953 by an Act of Parliament. the Commission recommended that at least 6% of the total budget of each academic institution should be set aside for the library. The Ranganathan Committee, appointed by the UGC in 1957,

made some outstanding recommendations, which included standards for library building and furniture, collection development, staff etc. The Kothari Commission also made valuable recommendations for this purpose.

The University Grants Commission played a vital role by “regularly providing appropriate grants and funds to all universities for development of libraries, to purchase books and journals. To promote the establishment and development of academic libraries, the UGC has appointed several committees and commissions over the last several years. These include:

- The Library Committee, 1957.
- Review Committee on Library Science, 1961.
- The Education Commission, 1964-66.

5.3.2. Information age

In this period, the quality of life as well as prospects for social change and economic development depend increasingly on information and its exploitation. With the advent and application of computers, services of libraries have changed. Computers are used in libraries to process, store, retrieve and disseminate information. This has redefined the concept of library from a house of books to a house without wall through the advent of the Internet and other electronic formats.

In this period the following Committee were established by UGC to promote academic libraries-

- Mehrotra Committee, 1983.
- Committee on National Network System for Universities Libraries (INFLIBNET), 1988.
- Curriculum Development Committee on Library and Information Science, 1990-93.

The Information and Library Network (INFLIBNET) set up by the UGC as an autonomous inter- university centre in 1991 to interlink the academic libraries. It is involved in modernizing university libraries in India and connects these to a nation-wide-high speed data network. The centre also developed ‘Software for University Libraries’ (SOUL), a library automation software making the manual work of library automated and easy. The UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortium facilitates current as well as archival access to more than 7,500 core and peer-reviewed electronic journals and 10 bibliographic databases access to e-

resources in almost all disciplines offered to universities having the Internet connectivity under the UGC-INFONET networking program.

The consortium came into existence in 1982 with emergence of the Forum for Resource Sharing in Astronomy and Astrophysics (FORSA). The Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India set up the Indian Digital Library in Engineering Science and Technology (INDEST) to provide access to e-resources to all the Indian Institutes of Technology (IITs), Indian Institute of Science (IISc) and other institutions including NITs, ISM, IIMs, NITTTRs, etc. The Consortium for e-Resources in Agriculture (CeRA) provides access to more than 3000 journals in the broad spectrum of agricultural sciences to agricultural universities, veterinary universities and Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) institutions. The National Knowledge Commission (NKC) was set up by the Government of India in 2005 for the growth and development of academic libraries to overcome core issues of academic libraries of India. (Chakraborty,2010)

6. Comparative study of academic libraries in different era

Era	Ancient (before 1200 AD)	MEDIEVAL PERIOD (1200 A.D. – 1799 A.D.)		Modern PERIOD (1800 A.D.-)		
Predominant characteristics		Early middle age (1200 A.D. – 1399 A.D.)	Renaissance (1400- 1799)	Industrial Age (1800-1950)		Information age (1981-)
	Colonial (1800- 1946)			Post- Colonial (1947-1980)		
Type of collection or subject field	Vedas, Samhitas, upanisads, Sutras, Buddhist philosophies , logic, grammar, medicine, yoga	Mainly Religious collections kept in Ashrams or Gurukuls, monasteries , palaces of the emperors	Different discipline or subjects	Different discipline or subjects	Different discipline or subjects or knowledge domain	Multi-lingual, multimedia documents on universe of knowledge
Medium of reading	Inscription on stone pillars and rocks, Palm leaf, unpublished records, manuscripts	Palm leave and parchment manuscript	Palm leave and parchment manuscript , later printed books	Printed books after the invention of printing press	Printed books, microforms, braille and spoken books	CD-DVD, computer, mobile, internet

Type of user	Educated society and some privileged few	Monks, nun, people related to academic works	people related to academic works- teachers, students, research scholars	people related to academic works- teachers, students, research scholars	people related to academic works- teachers, students, research scholars	people related to academic works- teachers, students, research scholars
Type of service	Personal or private collection, mainly storage and preservation work	Personal or group of privileged class	public	Library co-operation	Resource sharing	Library networking, remote access, open access
Patronage	King, rich persons	King, rich persons, Private funding	Private funding	Private funding	Government	Government
Retrieval process	No established retrieval process	No established retrieval process	primitive method of bibliographic control to locate and retrieve	Catalogue in book form	Catalogue in card form, sheaf form	OPAC, WEB-OPAC, advanced search strategies online
Great libraries of the time	Nalanda, palace library in Kashmir, Buddhist libraries at Tamralipta, Vikramsila, Odantapuri, Somapuri, Mithila, Vallabhi, Kanheri, Taxila	Imperial library by Sultan Jalal-Uddin at Delhi where Amir Khasru was the librarian, palace libraries of the Mughal emperors	Libraries of Maharaja chikka Deva Raya of Mysore and Maharaja Sawai Jai Singh II of Jaipur, Sanskrit College, Calcutta Medical College	Fort William college, Serampore Colleges, Calcutta, Madras and Bombay universities, Aligarh Muslim University	Establishment of higher education institutions like colleges and universities in India according to the UGC rules and regulations	Online repositories like NDLI, Consortia like e-Shodhsindhu by INFLIBNET

7. Findings

- i. In ancient India, academic libraries were rich with manuscripts on Vedas, Buddhist scripture and commentaries.

- ii. Those libraries were mainly adjacent to the universities, monasteries and palace of the emperors.
- iii. In medieval time, the growth of academic libraries decreased due to the invasions and political troubles.
- iv. The invention of printing machinery changes the world of learning.
- v. In modern period, the academic libraries revived its glory. The industrial revolution and arrival of renaissance opened new panorama of knowledge.
- vi. Prior to the arrival of technology libraries were bound to books and printed materials and information retrieval process was manual and time consuming.
- vii. With the advent of IT, libraries have a drastic change in forms and services giving access to information from anywhere at any time.

8. Conclusion

India is a vast repository of knowledge from ancient age, when the written literatures were kept in Ashrams or Gurukuls in the form of manuscripts. From the historical evidence and excavation, we come to know that the enriched library collections were destroyed by the invaders and all the treasure of knowledge and human endeavour went in vain. More research on this area should be done to find out and know our glorious past. Academic library is always the centre of learning and research for its users from the ancient to modern period. Advent of technology changed the shape and services of the library but it was and will always be the preserver of knowledge for the next generations.

References

- [1] Bhatt, R.K. (1995). History and Development of Libraries in India. Delhi: Mittal.
- [2] Chakraborty, B. (2010). Foundation of library and information science. Kolkata: World Press
- [3] Datta, B. K. (1970) Libraries and Librarianship of Ancient and Medieval India. Delhi: Atma Ram and Sons.

- [4] Kumar, S.(2014). Growth and development of library systems in india. International Journal of Innovative Social Science & Humanities Research, 1(1), pp. 162-172
- [5] Majumdar, R.C., Raychaudhuri, H.C. & Datta K. (1946). An Advanced History of India. MacMillian Press: London.
- [6] Ranganathan, S. R. “Radio Talk of April 1956. Mohamed Taher and Donald G. Davis, Jr. Librarianship and Library Science in India.
- [7] Sing, R.K. & Kumar, S.(2021) A historical study of libraries of Medieval India. International Journal of Scientific & Innovative Research Studies, 9(11), pp. 22-26.
- [8] Srivastava, S.N. and Verma, S.C. (1980). University Libraries in India. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers.
- [9] University education commission. (1949). Report. Delhi: Ministry of education.

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